

Metabolomic profiling and anti-inflammatory activity of *Blumea balsamifera*: Insights from in silico and in vitro studies

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Abstract

Blumea balsamifera is a medicinal plant with recognized anti-inflammatory properties. This study employed both LC-HRMS and GC-MS to comprehensively profile its ethanolic extract. Distinct analytical objectives were pursued: LC-HRMS was used for untargeted metabolomic profiling, identifying 134 bioactive compounds, including fatty acyls and flavonoids. GC-MS, in contrast, focused on detecting volatile constituents, which resulted in the identification of proximadiol, a major sesquiterpenoid. Proximadiol was detected in *B. balsamifera* from the Ie-Jue geothermal area and confirmed by both analytical techniques. In silico analysis highlighted cytokine-mediated signaling and the JAK-STAT pathway as pivotal mechanisms, with proximadiol demonstrating strong binding interactions with interleukin-related targets. Molecular docking results were further supported by protein stability analyses, reinforcing its potential role in modulating inflammatory processes. Protein denaturation and inhibition assays confirmed significant anti-inflammatory activity of the extract, comparable to aspirin, with IC_{50} values of 103.85 ppm for the denaturation assay and 97.23 ppm for the inhibition assay, respectively. The combination of computational predictions, protein stability data, and in vitro anti-inflammatory assays provides strong evidence for the bioactivity of *B. balsamifera*, supporting the need for further pharmacological and clinical evaluation.

Keywords

anti-inflammatory, Ie-Jue geothermal area, metabolomics, proximadiol, *Sembong*

Introduction

Medicinal plants have a longstanding history in traditional practices and are now receiving scientific scrutiny for their varied pharmacological actions. *Blumea balsamifera* (L.) DC., a member of the Asteraceae family, is a prominent medicinal plant in Southeast Asia, recognized for its traditional use in treating wounds, inflammation, and

bacterial infections (Wang et al. 2023). The plant, known as *sembong*, has been utilized in traditional medicine for its diuretic, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial properties (Y. Pang et al. 2014). Research indicates that *B. balsamifera* contains more than 100 phytochemical compounds, which can be classified into volatile and non-volatile categories (Widhiantara and Jawi 2021). Recent studies have identified active phytochemicals in the ethanolic extract

of *B. balsamifera*, including flavonoids, phenolics, and terpenoids, which exhibit potent antioxidant, antimicrobial, and anti-inflammatory properties. For instance, Ismail et al. (2022) reported that the plant extract demonstrated antimicrobial activities against various pathogenic microorganisms and contained multiple phytochemical constituents such as alkaloids, flavonoids, steroids, and cardiac glycosides. Similarly, other studies have highlighted that *B. balsamifera* possesses numerous biological activities, including antioxidant and antimicrobial effects, attributed to its rich phytochemical composition (Jirakitticharoen et al. 2022; Maulydia et al. 2023; Sari et al. 2023). These findings underscore the therapeutic potential of *B. balsamifera* in both traditional and modern medicine.

Major advances in many “omics,” including genomics, transcriptomics, proteomics, metabolomics, and phenomics, have occurred since the dawn of the twenty-first century (Patel et al. 2021). Recent advancements in metabolomics have facilitated the untargeted analysis of plant extracts, revealing several bioactive chemicals with potential medicinal uses. Untargeted metabolomics employs high-resolution analytical methods, including gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) and liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry (LC-MS), to identify and quantify the chemical components in plant extracts (Patel et al. 2021; Wu et al. 2021). These methods are particularly valuable in identifying the phytochemical diversity of medicinal plants like *B. balsamifera*, which contains significant amounts of borneol, quercetin, and phenolic acids (Jirakitticharoen et al. 2022; Masyudi et al. 2022; Maulydia et al. 2024a). The findings not only underscore the plant’s potential in treating inflammatory disorders but also establish a basis for drug discovery and development.

The anti-inflammatory effects of *B. balsamifera* have been increasingly studied, with evidence suggesting its ability to modulate key inflammatory pathways. Specifically, its phytochemical constituents inhibit pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α , IL-1 β , and IL-6, and reduce activation of the NF- κ B signaling pathway (Kong et al. 2020; Liao et al. 2021). Additionally, certain sesquiterpenoid esters isolated from *B. balsamifera* have demonstrated significant NO inhibitory activity, reinforcing its anti-inflammatory potential (Chen et al. 2010). Furthermore, its ability to suppress oxidative stress through antioxidant activity enhances its therapeutic value for inflammatory diseases (Y. Pang et al. 2014).

The integration of in silico methods, such as molecular docking and network pharmacology, with in vitro assays has furthered our understanding of how *B. balsamifera*’s phytochemicals interact with molecular targets. The purpose of this study is to investigate the potential effects of *B. balsamifera* metabolites arising from the manifestation of a geothermal environment as a geothermal-adapted species (Azhar et al. 2024; Harera et al. 2024; Idroes et al. 2025). Computational tools have identified potential binding affinities of compounds like borneol to key proteins in inflammatory pathways, such as Toll-like receptors and NF- κ B complexes (Liao et al. 2021). These methods complement experimental approaches by providing

mechanistic insights into the bioactive compounds’ interactions with key enzymes, receptors, and signaling molecules. For instance, network pharmacology has mapped pathways such as the TNF signaling cascade and toll-like receptor activation as critical targets of *B. balsamifera*’s anti-inflammatory compounds (Kong et al. 2020).

This study aims to employ untargeted metabolomics to profile the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* and evaluate its anti-inflammatory activity using in silico and in vitro methodologies. By providing insights into its bioactive components and their mechanisms of action, this research contributes to the growing evidence supporting the therapeutic potential of *B. balsamifera* in managing inflammatory conditions. Expanding our understanding of its untapped metabolomic potential will enable the development of more precise and efficacious treatments for inflammation-related conditions.

Materials and methods

Plant preparation and extraction process

At the geothermal location of Ie-Jue, Aceh Province, Indonesia (coordinates: 5°30'24"N, 95°37'45"E), *B. balsamifera* leaves were collected. The leaves were thoroughly cleaned and allowed to air dry at room temperature before being ground into a fine powder. A three-day maceration procedure was performed using ethanol at a weight-to-volume ratio (w:v) of 1:10. The plant material and solvent were maintained without replacement throughout the maceration period, with occasional stirring to enhance extraction efficiency. After 72 hours, the extract was filtered to remove plant residues. The solvent was then evaporated using a rotary evaporator (Büchi Rotavapor®, Switzerland) to obtain the crude ethanol extract.

Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis

A gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) analysis was performed on the extract of *B. balsamifera* in the study that we conducted previously (Maulydia et al. 2023). GC-MS was used to identify volatile and semi-volatile constituents in the extract, employing a single quadrupole (iSQ) 7000 mass spectrometer fitted with a Trace-GOLD TG-35MS column and coupled to a TRACE 1310 gas chromatograph (Maulydia et al. 2024b).

Liquid chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS) analysis

Untargeted metabolomic profiling was performed using liquid chromatography-high resolution mass spectrometry (LC-HRMS). This study involved metabolite identification by comparing retention times and searching mass lists using an online reference database. The LC-HRMS analysis utilized a Thermo Scientific Vanquish Horizon UH-PLC system coupled with an Orbitrap Exploris 240 mass

spectrometer. Chromatographic separation was conducted on an Accucore Phenyl Hexyl column (100 mm × 2.1 mm, 2.6 μm), maintained at 40 °C, with a mobile phase comprising water with 0.1% formic acid (Phase A) and acetonitrile with 0.1% formic acid (Phase B). The gradient elution began with 5% B, increasing to 90% over 16 minutes, holding for 4 minutes, and returning to initial conditions for equilibration within a 25-minute runtime at a flow rate of 0.3 mL/min. The injection volume was 5 μL. Mass spectrometry operated in both positive and negative ion modes, combining full scan and data-dependent fragmentation modes with resolutions of 60,000 and 22,500 FWHM, respectively. The scan range covered 70–800 m/z with a mass tolerance of 5 ppm and collision energies of 30, 50, and 70. The electrospray ionization source was optimized with spray voltages of 3500 V (positive) and 2500 V (negative), sheath gas at 35 Arbitrary Units (AU), auxiliary gas at 7 AU, sweep gas at 1 AU, and temperatures of 300 °C and 320 °C for the ion transfer tube and vaporizer, respectively. For sample preparation, 10 mg of material was dissolved in 1 mL of methanol, vortexed, diluted tenfold, and filtered through a 0.2 μm nylon membrane before analysis.

Metabolomic analysis

The metabolomic analysis focused on identifying and classifying the major compound groups present in the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera*. Metabolites were detected using Compound Discoverer 3.3 software (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA). The raw LC-HRMS data underwent pre-processing, including peak alignment, baseline correction, noise filtering, and deconvolution, to ensure data accuracy. Following detection, the identified metabolites were categorized into their respective compound classes, such as flavonoids, terpenoids, fatty acyls, and alkaloids. This classification was performed using MetaboAnalyst 6.0, which allowed for the enrichment analysis of compound classes rather than individual metabolites (Z. Pang et al. 2024).

Drug-likeness properties and target class analysis

The chemical properties of the selected compound from the highest percentage from GC-MS analysis, including the simplified molecular input line entry system (SMILES) string and relevant physicochemical properties, were prepared from the PubChem database (Kim et al. 2023) (<https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). Drug-likeness properties were evaluated from Indian Medicinal Plants, Phytochemistry, and Therapeutics, or IMPPAT 2.0 (Mohanraj et al. 2018) (<https://cb.imsc.res.in/imppat/home>), and target class analysis was conducted from SwissTargetPrediction (Daina et al. 2019) (<http://www.swisstargetprediction.ch>).

Network pharmacology

Disease-associated genes and proteins were retrieved from the Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM) database using the keyword “inflammation” (Hamosh et

al. 2005) (<https://omim.org>). Identified targets were filtered based on their relevance to the pathological process, eliminating redundant ones (Kairupan et al. 2025). The compound-target and pathway-target datasets were integrated to construct a network model. Cytoscape software was used for visualization and analysis of the network (Shannon et al. 2003). Networks were analyzed to identify hub nodes, key targets, or compounds based on topological properties such as degree, betweenness, and closeness centrality. Nodes represented compounds, targets, or pathways, while edges denoted interactions between them (Khairan et al. 2024; Pendong et al. 2024). Enrichment analysis was performed to identify biological pathways associated with the identified targets (Sailah et al. 2024). Pathways with significant enrichment scores (p -value < 0.05) were prioritized for further discussion. Interactive visualizations were generated to depict the compound-target-pathway relationships. Compound-target networks, target-pathway networks, and integrated networks were created to illustrate the interconnectedness of the components. These visualizations facilitated the identification of key nodes and pathways contributing to the therapeutic potential of the compounds. The enrichment of Gene Ontology (GO) and Kyoto Encyclopedia of Genes and Genomes (KEGG) pathways aimed to identify and interpret functional relationships in biological processes (BP), molecular functions (MF), and cellular components (CC) (Ashburner et al. 2000). GO and KEGG enrichment analyses were performed utilizing STRING (Szklarczyk et al. 2023) (<https://string-db.org>). The maximum p -value from the GO keywords and KEGG pathway was subsequently calculated using $-\log_{10}$ (p -value). Subsequently, the gathered results were visualized utilizing the SRPlot tool (Chinese Academy of Sciences, Beijing, China) to facilitate their understanding and analysis (Tang et al. 2023).

Molecular docking analysis

To evaluate the binding interactions between the one selected compound and target proteins from network pharmacology, molecular docking was conducted using a structured, systematic approach, including target preparation, ligand preparation, docking simulations, and analysis of docking results. (1) Target Protein Preparation: The three-dimensional structures of the target proteins were retrieved from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) (Berman et al. 2002). Proteins were refined by removing water molecules, heteroatoms, and any bound ligands using Biovia Discovery Visualizer (Biovia 2020). Hydrogen atoms were added, and the protonation states of amino acid residues were optimized for physiological pH conditions. Energy minimization was performed to stabilize the protein structure (Morris et al. 2009). (2) Ligand preparation: the three-dimensional structure of the selected compound was obtained from the PubChem database in SDF format (Kim et al. 2023). The structure was optimized for geometry using force field algorithms to achieve its lowest energy conformation using PyRx (Dallakyan 2010).

Protonation states were adjusted for physiological conditions, and partial atomic charges were assigned. (3) Docking protocol: docking simulations were carried out using Autodock Vina (Trott and Olson 2009). The binding site on the target protein was identified based on predictions using DoGSite3 (Graef et al. 2023). DoGSite3 is a grid-based approach that employs a difference of Gaussian filter to identify potential binding pockets, relying exclusively on the three-dimensional structure of macromolecules (considering protein and nucleic acid chains with more than 50 atoms) and subsequently dividing them into sub-pockets (Volkamer et al. 2010). A grid box was defined to encompass the active site, ensuring sufficient coverage for potential ligand interactions. Ligands were flexibly docked into the target site, while the receptor remained rigid to simulate biologically relevant interactions. (4) Scoring and post-docking analysis: binding free energy (BFE) values were calculated for each ligand-protein complex, reflecting the strength of interactions. Docking poses were ranked based on these scores, and the top conformations were visually examined to identify key interactions, such as hydrogen bonding, hydrophobic contacts, and π -stacking. Visualization of the conformation from the selected compound and receptor was done using PoseView (Schöning-Stierand et al. 2022).

Protein structure flexibility analysis

To account for the dynamic nature of the target proteins, flexibility analysis was performed using CABS-flex 2.0, a coarse-grained molecular dynamics tool (Kuriata et al. 2018). The highest binding free-energy complex identified from molecular docking was used as input for this analysis. CABS-flex employs a coarse-grained protein model, which reduces computational complexity while retaining essential structural and dynamic properties of the protein (Kmieciak et al. 2016). This approach enables the simulation of large-scale conformational changes and local fluctuations in protein structures. In the CABS model, $T = 1.0$ generally approximates the temperature of the crystal (native state), while $T = 2.0$ typically facilitates the complete unfolding of unrestrained small protein chains. This study

uses a temperature of 1.4. Thus, the reduced temperature is identical to the product of the Boltzmann constant and the actual temperature. The field “Number of cycles” (N_{cycle}) determines the total number of models saved in the trajectory to be equal to $20 \times N_{cycle}$. The N_{cycle} in this study was 250, resulting in 5000 models in the trajectory.

In vitro analysis

The protein inhibition assay and the protein denaturation assay were employed in vitro to assess the potential anti-inflammatory properties of the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera*.

Protein inhibition assay

To assess the inhibitory potential of the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* on proteins implicated in inflammation, a detailed protein inhibition assay was performed. The assay involved preparing a reaction mixture by combining 1 mL of 20 mM Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.4) with 1 mL of the plant extract at varying concentrations ranging from 100 to 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. A negative control (without extract) and a positive control (aspirin at an equivalent concentration range) were included to validate the inhibitory effect of the extract. To this solution, 0.06 mg of trypsin was added, and the mixture was incubated at 37 °C for 5 minutes to allow pre-reaction stabilization. Following this pre-incubation, 1 mL of a 0.8% (w/v) casein solution was introduced, and the resulting mixture was further incubated at the same temperature for an additional 20 minutes to facilitate enzymatic activity. The enzymatic reaction was halted by adding 2 mL of 70% perchloric acid, which precipitated unreacted casein and proteins. The supernatant was analyzed for absorbance at a wavelength of 210 nm using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Shimadzu, UV 2500, Shimadzu Suzhou Instruments Mfg. Co., Ltd., Jiangsu, China), with a buffer-only solution used as a blank to correct for background absorbance (Oyedapo and Famurewa 1995). All experiments were performed in triplicate to ensure reproducibility. The degree of inhibition of protein activity was quantified using the formula (1):

$$\text{percentage inhibition (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance control} - \text{Absorbance sample}}{\text{Absorbance control}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Albumin denaturation inhibition assay

To examine the effectiveness of the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* in inhibiting protein denaturation, a comprehensive study was conducted. This method involved preparing a reaction solution containing varying concentrations of the extract (100, 200, 300, 400, and 500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) combined with a 1% aqueous solution of bovine serum albumin (BSA). A blank sample containing only BSA and buffer (without plant extract) was used as the negative control to determine the baseline level of denaturation. A positive control (aspirin, 100–500 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was included as

a reference anti-inflammatory agent for comparison. The pH of the mixture was carefully adjusted to the optimal level using a minimal volume of 1N HCl to ensure the assay conditions mimicked physiological environments. The reaction mixture was initially incubated at a temperature of 37 °C for 20 minutes to allow the extract and protein to interact under stable conditions. Subsequently, the mixture was subjected to heat-induced stress by increasing the temperature to 51 °C and maintaining this temperature for an additional 20 minutes, simulating denaturation conditions. After heating, the samples were cooled to room temperature to allow protein aggregates to stabilize before

measurement. The turbidity of the resulting solution was then measured at a wavelength of 660 nm (Shimadzu, UV 2500, Shimadzu Suzhou Instruments Mfg. Co., Ltd., Jiangsu, China), providing a quantitative indication of

protein denaturation (Mizushima and Kobayashi 1968). All experiments were conducted in triplicate to ensure reproducibility and statistical reliability. The inhibition of albumin denaturation was calculated using the formula (2):

$$\text{percentage inhibition (\%)} = \frac{\text{Absorbance control} - \text{Absorbance sample}}{\text{Absorbance control}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

Statistical analysis

All measurements were reported as mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). The IC_{50} values (inhibitory concentration required to achieve 50% inhibition) were determined using linear regression analysis of concentration versus percentage inhibition. A best-fit line was generated, and the IC_{50} value was interpolated from the regression equation. Statistical analyses were conducted in triplicate to ensure reproducibility. A grouped bar chart was generated using Python to compare the anti-inflammatory properties of the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* with those of aspirin (positive control). A grouped bar chart was generated utilizing the matplotlib library (Hunter 2007). The x-axis denotes the activity (IC_{50}) categories, and the y-axis illustrates the activity values in ppm. Each bar signifies the activity of a singular compound within a specific category.

Results and discussion

A primary objective of metabolomics is to identify, both qualitatively and quantitatively, as many molecules as possible that are present in an organism. Information regarding the chemical composition of plant extracts can be obtained through the process of metabolic profiling. A total of 134 metabolites were detected in the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* leaves, with the top twenty of

these being seen in Table 1. This significantly broadened our understanding of the metabolites in *B. balsamifera* leaves. Previously, only a limited number of components—mainly phenolics, alkaloids, and volatile oils—had been documented (Widhiantara and Jawi 2021). The primary metabolic groups comprised phenylpropanoids and polyketides, benzenoids, hydrocarbons, organic acids and derivatives, organoheterocyclic compounds, prenol lipids, organic oxygen compounds, organic nitrogen compounds, and lipids and lipid-like molecules (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Overview of enriched metabolites' primary class from LC-HRMS analysis.

Table 1. Metabolites compound from LC-HRMS analysis.

No	Metabolites Name	Molecular Formula	RT (min)	Reference Ion	Area (counts in 10^8)
1	2,3-Dihydroxypropyl (9Z,12Z,15Z)-9,12,15-octadecatrienoate	$C_{21}H_{36}O_4$	13.905	Positive	95.932
2	15-oxo-11Z,13E-eicosadienoic acid	$C_{20}H_{34}O_3$	11.534	Negative	91.650
3	13S-hydroperoxy-9Z, 11E, 14Z-octadecatrienoic acid	$C_{18}H_{30}O_4$	9.364	Negative	90.021
4	Naringenin 7-O-beta-D-glucoside 6''-acetate	$C_{23}H_{24}O_{11}$	4.754	Negative	84.980
5	2-Hydroxycinnamic acid	$C_9H_8O_3$	4.007	Negative	83.796
6	Carnosol	$C_{20}H_{26}O_4$	13.484	Positive	83.532
7	OH-Diaponeurosporene glucoside ester	$C_{36}H_{54}O_6$	14.658	Negative	81.650
8	5-Ethyl-3,8-dimethyl-1,7-dihydroazulene	$C_{14}H_{18}$	7.557	Positive	79.186
9	N-jasmonoyl-isoleucine	$C_{18}H_{29}NO_4$	29.621	Negative	78.793
10	β -Ionone	$C_{13}H_{20}O$	11.396	Positive	78.045
11	Ambrettolic acid	$C_{16}H_{30}O_3$	11.902	Negative	76.414
12	2-Oxo-octadecanoic acid	$C_{18}H_{34}O_3$	12.238	Positive	73.886
13	Docosanedioic acid	$C_{22}H_{42}O_4$	13.323	Negative	65.509
14	Pimelic acid	$C_7H_{12}O_4$	3.031	Negative	51.159
15	Phylloquinone	$C_{31}H_{46}O_2$	18.237	Positive	47.230
16	Lucknolide A	$C_{10}H_{12}O_6$	1.333	Negative	43.184
17	α -Curcumene	$C_{15}H_{22}$	2.247	Positive	38.336
18	2,3-Dihydro-2,3-dihydroxybenzoate	$C_7H_8O_4$	1.951	Positive	33.012
19	Proximadiol	$C_{15}H_{28}O_2$	6.018	Positive	24.581
20	Quercetin	$C_{15}H_{10}O_7$	5.884	Negative	24.523

The identification of metabolites has evolved from traditional biochemical pathway assessments to advanced high-dimensional metabolomics, offering a robust approach for discovering and characterizing biomarkers associated with health and disease. As illustrated in Fig. 2, the predominant compounds identified from the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* belong to the following subclasses: fatty acyls (24), flavonoids (13), prenol lipids (15), steroids and steroid derivatives (10), phenols (4), cinnamic acids and derivatives (3), benzene and substituted derivatives (7), unsaturated hydrocarbons (2), triazinanes (1), cinnamyl alcohols (1), coumarins and derivatives (2), carboxylic acids and derivatives (6), carboximidic acids and derivatives (1), tetralins (1), indanes (1), naphthopyrans (1), dihydrofurans (1), tetrapyrroles and derivatives (1), benzodioxoles (1), macrolides and analogues (1), keto acids and derivatives (1), hydroxy acids and derivatives (1), saturated hydrocarbons (1), isoprenoids (1), benzopyrans (1), pyridines and derivatives (1), organooxygen compounds (3), organonitrogen compounds (1), glycerophospholipids (2) and glycerolipids (2). Two subclasses from this analysis showed the dominant metabolites: fatty acyl and flavonoid compounds. Fatty acyls, particularly long-chain fatty acids (LCFAs), play a significant role in modulating immune cell functions. They act as metabolic intermediates and are integral components

of cell membranes. Beyond these roles, LCFAs also function as signaling molecules that influence inflammation through various mechanisms depending on the type of fatty acid involved (Kotlyarov and Kotlyarova 2021). Fatty acyls with 24 metabolites, namely 3-hydroxytetradecanedioic acid, pimelic acid, arachidonic acid, erucic acid, eicosadienoic acid, 20-carboxy-leukotriene B4, 16-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid, 3-oxotetradecanoic acid, palmitic amide, 20-trihydroxy-leukotriene B4, 2-hydroxyhexadecanoic acid, jasmonic acid, ethyl tetradecanoate, ethyl oleate, dukunolide A, ethyl tiglate, diethylhexyl adipate, 2-hydroxy-22-methyltetraacosanoic acid, and 2-hydroxystearic acid.

Flavonoids are a large group of phenolic plant constituents. Flavonoids from the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* with 13 metabolite compounds: apigenin, hesperetin, quercetin, luteolin, eriodictyol, diosmetin, sakuranetin, 5-hydroxy-7,8-dimethoxyflavonol, malvidin 3-glucoside, and 3',4',5'-trihydroxy-3,7-dimethoxyflavone 5-glucoside. Both fatty acyls and flavonoids play crucial roles in regulating inflammation. Fatty acyls can either promote or inhibit inflammatory processes depending on their type and context of use. Flavonoids complement these effects by directly inhibiting inflammatory pathways and mediators. Together, these compounds represent potential therapeutic targets for managing inflammatory conditions.

Figure 2. Overview of enriched metabolites sub-class from LC-HRMS analysis.

The chemical profile of *B. balsamifera* was analyzed using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). A total of twenty-two distinct chemical compounds were identified in the extract, highlighting the plant's phytochemical diversity. Among the identified chemicals, one secondary metabolite, proximadiol (C₁₅H₂₈O₂), exhibited a notable retention time of 29.69 minutes, suggesting its prominence as a compound of interest. The compound showed a distinct chromatographic peak with a relative abundance of 41.76%, making it the predominant constituent in the extraction (Maulydia et al. 2023). These findings underscore the compound's potential significance regarding its relative concentration and its role in the plant's biological activity. Proximadiol was also identified in the LC-HRMS study, exhibiting an area of 24.581e8 counts. This value is derived from extracted ion chromatograms (XIC), which are generated by plotting the intensity of ions at specific mass-to-charge ratios (m/z) over time from a full mass spectrum collected during a chromatographic run. This process involves plotting the total intensity or base peak intensity of ions within a defined mass tolerance window around the target m/z value against time (Zhang and Zhao 2014). The results confirmed the presence of proximadiol in *B. balsamifera* from the Ie-Jue geothermal area, as determined by both GC-MS and LC-HRMS analyses.

The component known as proximadiol, which is also known as cryptomeridiol, is a naturally occurring substance that originates from *B. balsamifera* (Shirota et al. 2011). Proximadiol is known as a diuretic sesquiterpene and can be detected from a non-polar extract in *Cymbopogon schoenanthus* (Abdelsalam et al. 2017). Other studies confirm the presence of proximadiol in *Cryptomeria japonica* D. Don leaves, *Cupressus funebris* woods, the aerial part of *Dracocephalum moldavica* and *Dysphania botrys*, and the fruit, leaf, and stem of *Juniperus indica* with reported biological activities relevant to human health (Feizbakhsh et al. 2003; Chanotiya and Mathela 2007; Yamada and Yatagai 2007; Adams and Li 2008; Alaei and Mahna 2013).

One of the most important factors to consider when selecting compounds during the early stages of drug discovery is their drug-likeness. The drug-likeness properties of proxi-

madiol can be seen in Table 2. The compound demonstrates favorable drug-like properties and complies with key filters such as the Lipinski and Ghose rules and scores well on multiple other criteria. The only concern is a potential violation of the Pfizer 3/75 rule, which flags compounds with a high likelihood of toxicity. With a QEDw score of 0.74, the compound shows strong potential as a drug candidate (Bickerton et al. 2012), though some optimization might be needed to address the Pfizer rule violation (Mohanraj et al. 2018).

The target classes of proximadiol were evaluated using ligand-based target prediction from SwissTargetPrediction (Daina et al. 2019). As illustrated in the pie chart (Fig. 3), the different colors indicate different classes and numbers of targets with cytochrome P450 (4), electrochemical transporter (1), enzyme (11), family A-G protein-coupled receptor (12), kinase (23), lyase (11), membrane receptor (2), nuclear receptor (9), other cytosolic protein (2), other membrane protein (1), oxidoreductase (2), phosphatase (2), phosphodiesterase (1), primary active transporter (1), protease (7), secreted protein (2), transferase (2), and voltage-gated ion channel (3). The kinase class is predominant in the activity prediction of proximadiol. Human protein kinases play a crucial role in signal transduction and dysfunction that can lead to inflammatory and cancerous diseases. This enzyme family has emerged as one of the most important drug targets in the twenty-first century due to dysregulation of protein kinase activity in a variety of diseases (Roskoski 2023). Several functional targets from kinases in this study are tyrosine-protein kinase (JAK1, JAK2, JAK3, and TYK2), mitogen-activated protein kinase 14 (MAP3K14), MAP kinase ERK1 (MAPK3), and serine/threonine-protein kinase (PIM1 and PIM3). Research highlighting the importance of exploring the kinases family, particularly JAK family inhibitors, emphasizes their critical role in inflammatory and autoimmune responses, indicating that there is still potential for developing kinase-targeted drugs to treat various human diseases (Galvez-Llompert et al. 2021). With over 70 FDA-approved kinase-targeted medications in clinical use, kinase has emerged as a prominent target (Roskoski 2023).

Table 2. Drug-likeness properties of proximadiol.

Property name	Property value	Description
Number of Lipinski's rule of 5 violations	0	Absence of violations suggests favorable oral bioavailability concerning molecular weight, lipophilicity, and the presence of hydrogen bond donors and acceptors.
Lipinski's rule of 5	Passed	Indicates that proximadiol possesses drug-like physicochemical characteristics conducive to oral absorption.
Number of Ghose rule violations	0	The absence of violations indicates that the molecule adheres to the molecular characteristics commonly seen in approved pharmaceuticals.
Ghose rule	Passed	Demonstrates adherence to molecular weight, logP, molar refractivity, and atomic count necessary for drug-like properties.
Veber rule	Good	Suggests favorable oral bioavailability based on rotatable bonds and polar surface area.
Egan rule	Good	Predicts good passive membrane permeability, important for drug absorption.
GSK 4/400 rule	Good	Indicates favorable physicochemical properties for oral drug candidates, considering molecular weight and logP.
Pfizer 3/75 rule	Bad	Suggests possible solubility or permeability challenges, as the molecule fails to satisfy the threshold established for Pfizer's drug-likeness requirements.
Weighted quantitative estimate of drug-likeness (QEDw) score	0.74	A high QEDw score indicates an optimal equilibrium of drug-like characteristics.

Descriptions: All the property values from the IMPPAT database were evaluated using RDKit.

Figure 3. Target classes of proximiadiol with different colors indicating different classes.

According to the findings from network pharmacology, eleven proteins were identified to correlate with proximiadiol (Fig. 4). Among these proteins are tyrosine-protein kinase (JAK1), interleukin-10 (IL10), interleukin-24 (IL24), interleukin-6 receptor subunit alpha (IL6R), interleukin-22 receptor subunit alpha-1 (IL22RA1), interleukin-12 receptor (IL23R), granulocyte colony-stimulating factor receptor (CSF3R), interferon lambda receptor 1 (IFNLR1), SHC-transforming protein 1 (SHC1), interleukin-12 receptor subunit beta-2 (IL12RB2), leptin receptor (LEPR), interleukin-20 (IL20), and nuclear receptor ROR-gamma (RORC). With a very low FDR ($3.42e-19$) and 11 associated genes, the JAK-STAT signaling pathway (hsa04630) emerges as the most significant (Table 3). The JAK-STAT pathway is critical in mediating responses to cytokines, which are essential for immune regulation, growth, and hematopoiesis. The presence of genes such as IL12RB2, JAK1, and IL6R suggests a strong involvement in immune response regulation and links to inflammatory and autoimmune conditions. The involvement of 10 genes with a low FDR ($2.02e-14$) points to substantial activity in immune signaling, and cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction (hsa04060) facilitates communication between immune cells through cytokines, with proteins such as IL12RB2, IL10, and IL6R involved. The importance of this pathway underscores its role in immune modulation and inflammation (Rossato et al. 2007).

The KEGG pathways related to inflammation, including the JAK-STAT signaling pathway, cytokine-cytokine receptor interactions, and others, are critical in various inflammatory conditions (Table 3). The JAK-STAT signaling pathway is crucial for mediating responses to cytokines and growth

factors, influencing immune responses and inflammation. Dysregulation of this pathway is often observed in chronic inflammatory diseases. The JAK-STAT pathway is implicated in the pathogenesis of inflammatory bowel disease (IBD). The genes associated with the JAK/STAT signaling pathway play vital roles in regulating inflammatory processes across various conditions. Understanding their interactions enhances our knowledge of inflammation's underlying mechanisms and informs potential therapeutic approaches to treat related diseases effectively. The interplay between these genes within the JAK/STAT pathway underscores their collective impact on inflammatory processes. Increased expression of pro-inflammatory cytokines (e.g., IL-6, IL-23) activates the JAK/STAT pathway, promoting chronic inflammation observed in conditions like rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and inflammatory bowel disease (IBD) (Banerjee et al. 2017; Ramakrishnan et al. 2022; Xue et al. 2023). Genetic mutations or dysregulation of these receptors can lead to heightened inflammatory responses or impaired resolution of inflammation (Samra et al. 2024). Targeting components of the JAK/STAT pathway has emerged as a therapeutic strategy in managing autoimmune diseases by modulating these inflammatory signals (Banerjee et al. 2017).

JAK1 is a key player in the JAK-STAT signaling pathway, primarily associated with class II cytokine receptors, including those for IL-10. When IL-10 binds to its receptor complex, it activates JAK1 (along with TYK2), leading to the phosphorylation of STAT3, which mediates anti-inflammatory responses (Carey et al. 2012). This pathway is essential for regulating immune responses and maintaining homeostasis. IL-10 is a potent anti-inflammatory

Figure 4. Summary of network analysis from proximadiol-targeted immunomodulator genes and proteins.

Table 3. KEGG pathway analysis from the network.

KEGG ID	Description	False discovery rate	Protein count	Protein Name
hsa04630	JAK-STAT signaling pathway	3.42e-19	11	IL12RB2, IL22RA1, IL23R, IFNLR1, LEPR, IL20, IL6R, CSF3R, IL24, IL10, JAK1
hsa04060	Cytokine-cytokine receptor interaction	2.02e-14	10	IL12RB2, IL22RA1, IL23R, IFNLR1, LEPR, IL20, IL6R, CSF3R, IL24, IL10
hsa04061	Viral protein interaction with cytokine and cytokine receptor	4.46e-07	5	IL22RA1, IL20, IL6R, IL24, IL10
hsa05321	Inflammatory bowel disease	5.57e-06	4	IL12RB2, IL23R, RORC, IL10
hsa04659	Th17 cell differentiation	3.26e-05	4	IL23R, RORC, IL6R, JAK1
hsa05200	Pathways in cancer	0.00076	5	IL12RB2, IL23R, IL6R, CSF3R, JAK1
hsa01521	EGFR tyrosine kinase inhibitor resistance	0.00086	3	IL6R, SHC1, JAK1
hsa05140	Leishmaniasis	0.0408	2	IL10, JAK1

cytokine that modulates immune responses by inhibiting pro-inflammatory cytokine production. IL-10's interaction with JAK1 is critical for its function in suppressing inflammation and promoting tolerance during immune responses (Rossato et al. 2007). Overall, these findings reveal key signaling pathways where specific genes modulate immune responses, inflammation, and disease states, offering valuable insights for potential therapeutic targets across inflammatory, autoimmune, and oncologic diseases. The high significance of the JAK-STAT and cytokine interactions underscores the central role of cytokine signaling in health and disease.

Fig. 5 provides insights into the functional roles and locations of key proteins involved in immune-related inflammation signaling, particularly focusing on cytokine interactions. Each row represents a Gene Ontology (GO) term, with associated significance values and protein counts, including biological process (BP: red dot), molecular function (MF: blue dot), and cellular component (CC: green dot). The data collectively highlights an integrated immune response, where proteins interact with cytokines at the cell surface to initiate signal transduction pathways, enabling cellular responses to external threats

or inflammatory signals. The cytokine-mediated signaling pathway ($-\log_{10}(\text{FDR})$ 7, with 8 proteins involved) and cellular response to cytokine stimulus ($-\log_{10}(\text{FDR})$ 6, with 9 proteins) are highlighted as highly significant processes. These terms indicate active pathways where cells respond to cytokines, which are crucial signaling molecules for immune responses and inflammation. Cytokines play a crucial role in both adaptive and innate immunity by triggering cell signaling pathways, notably the JAK-STAT pathway, which leads to gene activation and cellular responses vital for maintaining immune balance (Gadina et al. 2017). Disruptions in the signaling of cytokine receptors can cause immune system imbalances, leading to autoimmune disorders and persistent inflammatory conditions. Consequently, focusing on cytokine pathways, especially the JAK-STAT pathway, has emerged as an effective therapeutic strategy for treating these immune-related diseases. The emphasis on cytokine receptor activity and binding underscores the primary role of these proteins in detecting cytokines, making them central to immune response regulation. Cytokine receptor activity plays a central role, with receptors on the cell surface initiating responses to extracellular cytokine signals. Any

Figure 5. GO enrichment including biological process (red dot), molecular function (blue dot), and cellular component (green dot).

dysregulation here could lead to inflammatory responses or immune escape mechanisms, particularly in cancers (Lee and Rhee 2017). Additionally, their specific localization to plasma membrane complexes facilitates their role as mediators between the external environment and intracellular responses, essential for immune system function. These insights could be valuable in understanding immune response mechanisms and identifying potential therapeutic targets for immune-related diseases.

Molecular docking analysis was conducted using eleven receptors. Table 4 shows the binding free energy values of various proteins in relation to their ligands, with each protein identified by its name and PDB ID. The binding free energy (BFE) value, expressed in kcal/mol, reflects the strength of the interaction, with more negative values indicating more stable and stronger binding (Mauludya et al. 2022). For instance, JAK1 (PDB ID: 6DBN) shows the most negative value at -7.1 kcal/mol, indicating a particularly strong interaction among the proteins listed. Conversely, IL22RA1 (PDB ID: 3DLQ) has a binding energy of -5.5 kcal/mol, suggesting a weaker binding compared to others. Other proteins, such as IL12RB2 (PDB ID: 8XRP) at -6.8 kcal/mol, IFNLR1 (PDB ID: 5T5W) at -6.1 kcal/mol, and IL6R (PDB ID: 1P9M) at -6.2 kcal/mol, show moderate to strong binding energies, though still less intense than JAK1. Overall, the data provides a spectrum of binding affinities, from the strongest interaction with JAK1 to the weaker interaction with IL22RA1, which may offer valuable insights into protein-ligand interactions for applications in drug discovery in immunomodulatory effects. Visualization of interactions between proximadiol and eleven receptors can be seen in Fig. 6. In JAK1, proximadiol engages in hydrogen bonding with the N-H group of leucine 959 and forms Van der Waals contacts with leucine 1010 and valine 889. These interactions contribute to the overall binding affinity and specificity of proximadiol for JAK1, which is significant in the context of its role in signaling pathways and potential therapeutic applications.

The precise nature of these interactions can influence the efficacy of inhibitors targeting JAK1 in various diseases, including autoimmune disorders and cancers.

Table 4. Molecular docking analysis of proximadiol and eleven receptors.

No	Protein name	PDB ID	Binding free-energy value (Kcal/mol)
1	IL12RB2	8XRP	-6.8
2	IL22RA1	3DLQ	-5.5
3	IL23R	6WDQ	-5.9
4	IFNLR1	5T5W	-6.1
5	LEPR	3V6O	-5.9
6	IL20	4D0H	-6.1
7	IL6R	1P9M	-6.2
8	CSF3R	2D9Q	-6.0
9	IL24	6DF3	-6.2
10	IL10	2H24	-6.3
11	JAK1	6DBN	-7.1

Protein structure flexibility was evaluated using root mean square fluctuation (RMSF). The RMSF data for the JAK1 protein complexed with proximadiol provides insights into the structural flexibility and stability of various regions within the protein over the simulation (Fig. 7). The presence of proximadiol in the JAK1 complex (Fig. 7a), as reflected by lower RMSF values in crucial binding regions, suggests that proximadiol stabilizes the JAK1 structure. This rigidity implies a strong binding affinity, a typical hallmark of effective inhibitors that often achieve inhibition by reducing the movement of active site residues. The RMSF values for IL12RB2 in the proximadiol-bound state are higher or more variable than those for JAK1; this could indicate that proximadiol has a less stabilizing effect on IL12RB2, potentially due to differences in binding affinity or interaction dynamics (Fig. 7b). A less pronounced reduction in RMSF values suggests that proximadiol might not inhibit IL12RB2 as strongly or stably as JAK1. Therefore, RMSF analysis supports the idea that proximadiol may act as a stabilizing, potentially inhibitory ligand, with the capability to modulate JAK1's structural dynamics and possibly its activity. In comparing both complexes, the lower RMSF values in the JAK1-proximadiol complex suggest that proximadiol stabilizes JAK1 more effectively than IL12RB2. This greater stabilization likely corresponds to a higher binding affinity and greater inhibitory potential for JAK1, while IL12RB2 may retain more flexibility and function. Such RMSF differences support the potential for proximadiol to serve as a selective inhibitor for JAK1, providing insight into its possible applications in targeted therapy.

The in vitro data compares the efficacy of the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera* and aspirin in two assays: protein inhibition to measure the compound's ability to inhibit protein activity related to inflammation and protein denaturation to assess the prevention of protein denaturation, another hallmark of anti-inflammatory potential (Khairan et al. 2024). The ethanolic extract of

Figure 7. Fluctuation plot of two complex proteins and proximadiol. Description: RMSF in Å unit.

B. balsamifera exhibited 103.85 ppm for protein inhibition and 97.23 ppm for protein denaturation. Aspirin, the positive control, showed values of 57 ppm and 62 ppm for protein inhibition and protein denaturation, respectively (Fig. 8). The results highlight the anti-inflammatory potential of the ethanolic extract of *B. balsamifera*. Similar bioactivities have been observed for other plant-derived compounds from *B. balsamifera* that influence inflammatory responses, such as sesquiterpenoids, flavonoids, and essential oils (Chen et al. 2010; Liao et al. 2021). The anti-inflammatory properties of meso-eudesmol B from *Mesona procumbens* Hemsley, which is a 2-OBz proximadiol, were superior to those of other compounds, as evidenced by their EC_{50} value of 12.9 μ M, which was twice as potent as quercetin (Huang et al. 2022). This suggests that the plant extract could serve as a natural alternative or complement to synthetic drugs in managing inflammation. Further research, including mechanistic studies and in vivo assays, could strengthen its case for therapeutic application.

Conclusion

This study highlights the untargeted metabolomic profile and anti-inflammatory activity of the ethanolic

Figure 8. Comparison of protein inhibition and denaturation activities.

extract of *Blumea balsamifera*. Using LC-HRMS and GC-MS analyses, 134 bioactive compounds, including flavonoids, terpenoids, and phenolic acids, were identified, with proximadiol emerging as a key sesquiterpenoid. Molecular docking and protein stability analyses revealed strong binding interactions of proximadiol with interleukin-related targets, implicating the JAK-STAT signaling pathway as a pivotal mechanism. Protein denaturation and inhibition assays further validated the extract's significant anti-inflammatory activity, comparable to aspirin, with IC_{50} values of 103.85 ppm (protein inhibition) and 97.23 ppm (protein denaturation). These findings underscore the therapeutic relevance of *B. balsamifera* as a natural source of anti-inflammatory agents, providing a foundation for its integration into pharmacological research and potential clinical applications.

Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

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Author contributions

NBM: performed computational experiments, collected and analyzed data, and drafted the manuscript; KK and TET: supervised, analyzed data, and revised the manuscript; RI: supervised and revised the manuscript.

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